

Lexical Thresholds in Medical English - Vocabulary Recognition and Reading Comprehension

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between medical vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension in English for Medical Purposes (EMP) among second-year medical students. A cohort of 115 students at MU Varna, all with prior knowledge of biochemistry, completed a 45-item test comprising 25 vocabulary recognition items and 20 reading comprehension questions based on two biochemistry texts. The study examines overall performance, the relationship between lexical knowledge and comprehension, and the efficiency with which learners transfer vocabulary knowledge to reading tasks. Results show high overall performance, with mean scores of 93% for vocabulary and 88% for comprehension. A moderate positive correlation ($r = .56$) was found between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension, indicating that lexical knowledge is an important but not sufficient predictor of reading success. A transfer-efficiency measure ($M = 0.94$) suggests that students generally apply their vocabulary knowledge effectively, though with notable individual variation. Differences in performance between the two texts further indicate that factors such as textual complexity influence comprehension outcomes. The findings support a view of lexical coverage as a functional range rather than a fixed threshold, suggesting that recognition of approximately 90–93% of targeted domain-specific vocabulary appears sufficient under conditions of prior content familiarity. The study contributes to research on specialized L2 reading by providing empirical evidence from a medical ESP context.

Keywords

English for Medical Purposes; lexical coverage; vocabulary knowledge; reading comprehension; lexical threshold;

Introduction

Recent research suggests that effective L2 reading in specialized domains depends on achieving a high proportion of known words rather than surpassing an arbitrary “lexical threshold.” For example, advanced L2 readers generally require around 90–95% lexical coverage of a text to understand it well (Song & Reynolds, 2022; Pellicer-Sánchez et al., 2024), but understanding improves steadily with coverage rather than abruptly. Studies also show that *receptive* vocabulary knowledge (recognition and depth of understanding) is more predictive of reading success than productive knowledge (Tong et al., 2023). We review how cognitive processing efficiency relates to lexical coverage (Pellicer-Sánchez et al., 2024), and how English for Medical Purposes (EMP) courses emphasize discipline-specific vocabulary. Methodological issues—such as ceiling effects and text difficulty—complicate identifying a precise coverage “cutoff.” This theory motivates our study: by testing Bulgarian medical students with well-known biochemistry content in English, we examine their vocabulary–comprehension relationship and efficiency of applying known vocabulary, addressing our research questions on performance, vocabulary influence, and lexical transfer.

Lexical Knowledge in L2 Reading

Vocabulary size is widely recognized as critical to L2 reading comprehension (Tong et al., 2023). Learners with larger English vocabularies generally understand texts more accurately. In ESP contexts like medical reading, students often already grasp the concepts in their first language but must map these to English terms. Consequently, comprehension hinges on recognizing most key domain terms. If core technical words

are unknown, meaning breaks down (Song & Reynolds, 2022; Pellicer-Sánchez et al., 2024). Thus high vocabulary coverage of specialized terms is a prerequisite for processing content-rich texts.

Lexical Coverage as a Functional Range

Traditionally, figures such as 95–98% known words have been cited as a necessary “threshold” for L2 reading (Hu & Nation, 2000). However, recent evidence favors a more nuanced view of coverage as a functional range. Song and Reynolds (2022) showed that incremental gains in coverage steadily boosted comprehension scores for narrative and expository texts, without a sharp cutoff point. They found that around 98% coverage was reasonable for narratives and full coverage for expository texts (when background knowledge was low), but lower coverage still yielded substantial understanding. Similarly, Durbahn et al. (2024) manipulated coverage in audiovisual texts and observed that *optimal* comprehension occurred near 95% coverage, while minimal adequate comprehension could occur around 80%. These studies suggest that instead of a strict lexical threshold, learners benefit from higher coverage levels throughout a range (Pellicer-Sánchez et al., 2024). In short, comprehension improves as coverage rises, and exact requirements may vary by text type and reader proficiency (Song & Reynolds, 2022; Durbahn et al., 2024).

Receptive vs. Productive Vocabulary

Vocabulary knowledge is multidimensional. The distinction between *receptive* knowledge (recognizing a word in context) and *productive* knowledge (being able to use it) is fundamental. In reading tasks, receptive knowledge is the crucial driver: knowing a word’s meaning when encountered matters more than being able to actively produce it. Empirical studies support this: Tong et al. (2023) found that learners’ receptive vocabulary breadth and depth were strongly linked to their reading proficiency, whereas their productive vocabulary had far weaker effects. In practice, this implies that students can read successfully if they recognize most terms, even if they could not spell or define them in production. Moreover, depth of receptive knowledge (e.g. understanding synonyms, collocations, word forms) further aids comprehension (Tong et al., 2023). In our study we therefore focus on receptive (recognition) knowledge of the target medical terms, which is the more relevant dimension for reading.

Processing Efficiency and Vocabulary Transfer

The concept of *transfer efficiency* relates to how effectively learners apply known vocabulary during reading. Cognitive Load Theory helps explain this: when lexical coverage is low, readers’ attention is split across many unknown words, reducing processing efficiency (Pellicer-Sánchez et al., 2024). By contrast, higher coverage frees cognitive resources to integrate meaning and infer unknown terms. Pellicer-Sánchez and colleagues (2024) observed that texts at 98% coverage were read with less effort (longer saccades, faster reading) than texts at 90–95% coverage. In other words, known words serve as anchors, enabling more efficient processing of the remaining new words. Individual differences matter here: some students make more effective use of their vocabulary knowledge than others. For example, even with similar vocabulary scores, stronger readers may infer unknown meanings from context better than weaker readers. We capture this efficiency in our “transfer efficiency” metric: a high value indicates that a student converted most of their vocabulary knowledge into comprehension. Our data (as we will report) show variation in transfer efficiency, confirming that knowledge alone does not guarantee equal comprehension.

English for Medical Purposes and Domain Vocabulary

In medical education, students must learn a specialized lexicon as part of their ESP curriculum. EMP courses typically focus on reading authentic medical texts and acquiring relevant terminology (Zolfaghari et al., 2025). Because the biomedical concepts are already known from prior study, the challenge is learning and recognizing the English labels for those concepts. To support this, researchers have developed discipline-specific word lists. For example, Lei and Liu (2016) created a Medical Academic Vocabulary List (MAVL) highlighting high-frequency medical terms (Medical Academic Vocabulary List; MAVL). Teachers often assume that mastering such medical terms (at least receptively) is key to accessing content. In our context, Bulgarian students have strong biochemistry knowledge in L1, so reading an English biochemistry passage requires mapping that knowledge onto English vocabulary. English proficiency remains the bottleneck. This aligns with observations that EMP instruction “focuses on reading comprehension of medical texts and some basic medical vocabulary” (Zolfaghari et al., 2025). However, empirical studies linking specialized vocabulary size to actual comprehension in medical domains are still scarce. Our study directly addresses this by testing how much students’ knowledge of targeted medical terms supports their understanding of biochemistry texts.

Methodological Considerations and Research Gaps

Recent studies also highlight methodological issues in estimating lexical requirements. Many experiments use only highly proficient students or simplified texts, leading to ceiling effects (Song & Reynolds, 2022). In our data we similarly saw near-ceiling scores on the easier passage, which limits variance. Additionally, textual features matter: Song and Reynolds (2022) found genre differences (narrative vs expository), and our own two biochemistry texts differed in difficulty despite similar vocabulary. This suggests that text complexity can influence how many words need to be known. To isolate vocabulary effects, future research should manipulate coverage levels and difficulty systematically, and include lower-proficiency groups. In sum, high lexical coverage appears necessary for medical ESP reading, but it is only one factor. Other variables – text structure, reader strategies, and prior knowledge – also shape comprehension. No single study has resolved how these interact, indicating a gap for targeted experimental work.

Present Study and Research Questions

The reviewed literature suggests that our medical students likely operate within a high-coverage range for comprehension, but that no fixed “threshold” alone determines success. Based on these insights, we investigate Bulgarian second-year medical students reading English passages on known biochemistry topics. By choosing familiar content, we hold conceptual knowledge constant and isolate lexical processing. We will measure each student’s recognition of targeted medical vocabulary and their comprehension of two texts, computing (a) overall performance and (b) the ratio of comprehension to vocabulary knowledge (transfer efficiency). This design directly addresses our research questions: (1) How well do students comprehend familiar biomedical texts in English? (2) To what extent does knowledge of medical vocabulary predict comprehension? (3) Do students effectively transfer their known vocabulary into understanding? Answers will clarify whether ~90% coverage suffices in medical ESP and how learners utilize their vocabulary when reading in a second language.

Methods

Participants

The study involved 115 second-year medical students at MU Varna. All participants had successfully completed their biochemistry courses prior to the study, ensuring that the conceptual content of the texts was familiar. Students came from a range of educational backgrounds, including English-language high

schools, other-language high schools, and extended English programs in secondary education. Participation was voluntary, and all students completed the test under standard classroom conditions.

Materials

Two texts were selected from *Harvey and Ferrier's Biochemistry* (5th edition) that focused on amino acids and related biochemical concepts. From these texts, 25 domain-specific lexical items were extracted from the Final 50 Medical Academic Vocabulary List (MAVL) for targeted assessment. A total of 45 test items were designed: 25 vocabulary questions to assess word recognition, and 20 comprehension questions (10 per text) to evaluate understanding of the texts. Vocabulary items required students to match terms with definitions, while comprehension items focused on identifying key information and drawing basic inferences from the texts.

Procedure

The test was administered in a single session during regular class time. Students completed all 45 items individually, without access to reference materials. Responses were collected and scored using a pre-defined key. Vocabulary scores were calculated as the number of correct matches out of 25, while comprehension scores were calculated as the number of correct responses per text, and combined across both texts. Transfer efficiency was calculated to estimate the extent to which students applied their vocabulary knowledge to reading comprehension, using the ratio of comprehension performance to vocabulary knowledge.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including means, medians, standard deviations, and score ranges, were calculated for vocabulary, comprehension, and combined scores. Proportional scores were also computed to allow comparison across measures. The relationship between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension was examined using a correlation coefficient. Transfer efficiency was analyzed to assess how effectively students applied their lexical knowledge when completing comprehension tasks. All analyses were conducted using standard statistical methods, and results are reported in the following section.

Results

The performance of the cohort was consistently high across all components of the test, providing a clear basis for addressing the three research questions. On the full forty-five-item instrument, students achieved a mean score of 40.85, with a median of 42 and a relatively narrow standard deviation of 3.88. Scores ranged from 28 to the maximum possible 45, indicating that most participants performed near the upper end of the scale, with limited dispersion. In response to the first research question, these results show that the cohort performed strongly overall, with the majority of students demonstrating high levels of accuracy across both vocabulary and reading tasks.

A similarly strong pattern emerged in the vocabulary component. On the twenty-five-item section targeting medical lexical items, the mean score was 23.31, corresponding to an average proportional accuracy of 0.93, with a median of 24 and a standard deviation of 1.73. While most students approached ceiling performance, the observed minimum of 16 indicates that a subset of participants had more limited lexical knowledge. Overall, the distribution suggests that the cohort possessed a high level of receptive recognition of the target medical vocabulary.

Reading comprehension performance, while also strong, showed greater variability and a clear distinction between the two texts. On the first text, students achieved a mean score of 9.25 out of 10, corresponding to

a proportional mean of 0.93, with a median at the maximum value. In contrast, performance on the second text was lower, with a mean of 8.29 and a proportional mean of 0.83, alongside a wider range of scores extending down to 2. When the results from both texts are combined, the mean comprehension score is 17.54 out of 20, or 0.88 in proportional terms, with a broader distribution than that observed for vocabulary. This pattern indicates that, although comprehension was generally high, it was more variable and sensitive to text-related factors.

The relationship between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension directly addresses the second research question. Correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive relationship ($r = .56$) between vocabulary scores and combined comprehension scores. This indicates that students with higher levels of lexical knowledge tended to achieve better results on reading tasks. At the same time, the strength of the correlation suggests that vocabulary knowledge, while an important contributing factor, does not fully determine comprehension performance.

In order to examine the extent to which lexical knowledge was actively applied during reading, a transfer-efficiency measure was calculated. The mean value of this measure was 0.94, with a median of 0.97 and a range from 0.45 to 1.33. Values close to 1 indicate that students were generally able to utilize their vocabulary knowledge effectively when completing comprehension tasks, while lower values reflect less efficient transfer. The observed variation suggests that the ability to apply lexical knowledge differs across individuals, thereby providing an answer to the third research question: students do use vocabulary knowledge in reading, but the efficiency of this transfer is not uniform.

The results suggest that the cohort operated above a functional lexical threshold, with mean vocabulary knowledge at approximately 93%, supporting high levels of reading comprehension (88%). While the present data do not allow for the identification of a precise threshold level, the findings are consistent with the view that high levels of lexical coverage—likely in the range of 90% or above for the targeted items—facilitate successful comprehension in medical ESP texts.

Measure	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD
Word Score (max 25)	23.31	24	16	25	1.73
Word Score (%)	93	96	64	100	7
Text 1 Score (max 10)	9.25	10	5	10	1.09
Text 1 Score (%)	93	100	50	100	11
Text 2 Score (max 10)	8.29	9	2	10	0.94
Text 2 Score (%)	83	90	20	100	19
Combined Text Score (%)	88	90	40	100	13
Transfer Efficiency	94	97	45	133	12
Vocabulary–Comprehension Correlation	0.56	-	-	-	-

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Vocabulary and Reading comprehension

Note: Scores for vocabulary and comprehension are reported both as raw totals and proportion correct. Transfer efficiency represents the ratio of comprehension performance to vocabulary knowledge. Correlation represents Pearson's r between vocabulary and combined comprehension scores.

Overall, the results show that the cohort performed strongly, that vocabulary knowledge is moderately associated with reading comprehension, and that learners are generally able to transfer lexical knowledge to comprehension tasks, albeit with varying degrees of efficiency.

Note: Vocabulary-Comprehension correlation ($r = 0.56$)

Figure 1. Performance of second-year medical students on vocabulary and reading comprehension tasks. Scores are shown as percentages for word recognition (Word Score), comprehension for Text 1 and Text 2, combined comprehension (Combined Text), and transfer efficiency, representing the extent to which vocabulary knowledge was applied during reading.

Discussion

The results of the present study indicate that the cohort performed consistently well across both vocabulary and reading components, reflecting a high level of familiarity with the subject matter. As all participants had already successfully completed their biochemistry coursework, the content of the texts was not new to them. In this context, the primary variable under investigation was not conceptual understanding, but the ability to access and process this knowledge through English.

The high scores in the vocabulary section suggest that most students possessed a strong level of receptive knowledge of the targeted medical terms. At the same time, reading comprehension scores, while also high, were slightly lower and more variable. This pattern indicates that even when content knowledge is established, successful comprehension in English depends on sufficient lexical access.

The relationship between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension was moderate, which suggests that lexical knowledge plays a meaningful role, but does not fully account for performance differences. Given

the shared disciplinary background of the cohort, variation in comprehension is likely related to differences in language processing rather than differences in subject knowledge.

A key observation emerging from the data is that high levels of vocabulary knowledge appear to be associated with successful comprehension under these conditions. The cohort achieved an average vocabulary score of approximately 93%, alongside a mean comprehension score of 88%. This suggests that, in order to engage effectively with the texts, students needed to recognize a substantial proportion of the relevant lexical items. In practical terms, the results indicate that vocabulary knowledge in the range of approximately 90–93% of the targeted items was sufficient to support generally successful comprehension for this group.

At the same time, the difference in performance between the two texts shows that vocabulary knowledge alone does not fully determine outcomes. The lower and more variable scores on the second text suggest that factors such as textual complexity or processing demands may influence comprehension, even when lexical coverage is relatively high.

The transfer-efficiency measure further supports this interpretation. While the average value indicates that students were generally able to apply their vocabulary knowledge in context, the observed variation suggests that this process is not uniform. Some students appear to make more effective use of their lexical knowledge than others, even when overall vocabulary scores are similar.

Overall, the findings suggest that, for students with established subject knowledge, a high level of vocabulary recognition is an important condition for successful reading in medical ESP. However, it should be viewed as one contributing factor among several, rather than as a sufficient explanation on its own.

Limitations

Several limitations should be noted. First, the sample consisted of a relatively homogeneous group of medical students with prior knowledge of biochemistry, which limits the generalizability of the findings to other proficiency levels or non-specialist populations.

Second, ceiling effects were observed in both vocabulary and comprehension scores, particularly for the first text. This reduced variability may have attenuated the strength of the observed relationship between vocabulary knowledge and comprehension.

Third, lexical coverage was operationalized through a limited set of targeted medical terms rather than total text coverage. As such, the reported percentages reflect knowledge of domain-specific items rather than overall lexical coverage.

Finally, the transfer-efficiency measure represents an exploratory metric and should be interpreted with caution, as it has not been independently validated and may reflect factors beyond lexical processing alone.

Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between medical vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension in a cohort of second-year medical students with prior biochemistry knowledge. The results indicate that students generally require recognition of approximately 90–93% of the targeted lexical items to engage effectively with the texts in English. While comprehension was high overall, variation between texts and among students suggests that vocabulary knowledge alone does not fully determine reading outcomes. The findings highlight the importance of sufficient lexical coverage as a condition for comprehension, rather than as a sole explanatory factor. These results provide a baseline for further investigation, including the potential effects of text adaptation and simplification in medical ESP reading.

References:

- Durbahn, M., Rodgers, M. P. H., Macis, M., & Peters, E. (2024). Lexical coverage in L1 and L2 viewing comprehension. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 46(4), 1045–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263124000391>
- Pellicer-Sánchez, A., Webb, S., & Wang, A. (2024). How does lexical coverage affect the processing of L2 texts? *Applied Linguistics*, 45(6), 953–972. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amae062>
- Song, T., & Reynolds, B. L. (2022). The effect of lexical coverage on L2 learners' reading comprehension of narrative and expository genres. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 59, Article 101154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2022.101154>
- Tong, Y., Hasim, Z., & Halim, H. A. (2023). The relationship between L2 vocabulary knowledge and reading proficiency: The moderating effects of vocabulary fluency. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10, 555. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02058-2>
- Xodabande, I., Ebrahimi, H., & Karimpour, S. (2022). How much vocabulary is needed for comprehension of video lectures in MOOCs: A corpus-based study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 992638. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.992638>
- Yildiz, M. (2023). Lexical coverage required for minimal and optimal levels of reading comprehension in the English tests of the Higher Education Institutions Examination. *rEFLECTIONS*, 30(3), 695–718.
- Zolfaghari, Z., Karimian, Z., Zarifsanaiey, N., & Farahmandi, A. Y. (2025). Navigating challenges in medical English learning: Leveraging technology and gamification for interactive education – a qualitative study. *BMC Medical Education*, 25, Article 1045. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-025-07511-1>

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Appendix A: Medical Academic Vocabulary List (MAVL):

cell, data, muscular, significant, clinic, analyze, respond, factor, method, protein, tissue, dose, gene, previous, demonstrate, normal, process, similar, concentrate, function, therapy, indicate, area, obtain research, vary. activate, require, induce, cancer, occur, role, evident, range identify, period, outcome, phase, specific, liver, infect, culture, mediate, score, affect, potential, individual, expose, involve, survive, target respective, intervene, site, per, design, primary, approach, estimate, component, acid, baseline, procedure, overall, pathway, inflammation, region, participate, lesion, technique, volume, serum, define, evaluate, prior, assay, injury, section, task, achieve, symptom, detect, molecular, error, incubate, donor, intense, chronic, fraction, insulin, contrast, react, source, available, disorder, positive, structure, multiple generate, conclude, medium, inhibit, complex, distribute, major, tumor, initial, channel, receptor, membrane, stress, strain, nuclear, ration, approximate, release, transparent, surgery, assess, impact, versus, drug, laboratory, minimize, reveal, scan, monitor, criterion, visual, duration, cycle, investigate, acute, sequence, select, maximize, whereas, peak, elevation, image, enzyme, parameter, isolate, mutation, enhance, calcium, glucose, appropriate, incience, conduit, protocol, background, stimulate, algorithm, establish, efficacy, hypothesis, feature, interal, mortality, array, derive, series, buffer, specimen, focus, display, plasma, abstract, grade, secondary, strategy, graft, undergo, peripheral, transcription, despite, consist, status, furthermore, immune, reverse, infuse, author, interact, issue, negatie, thouthout, goal, vein chamber, independent, proliferation, formation, subsequent, predict, correspon, correlate, regulate, exclude, metabolic, device, recruit, final, impair, inject, percent, publish, remove, syndrome, exhibi, blot, defect, biopsy, index, diameter, cognitive, followup, fluid, lipid, magnetic, margin, energy, locate, survey, software, profile, attribute, convention, synthesis, recover, objective, filter, segment, compound, link, guideline, extract, proportion, regression, questionnaire, discharge, respiratory, gender, summary, promote, tract, toxic, relevant, episode, acquire, communicate, internal, dimension, layer, microscope, adverse, recipient, density, virus, interpret, document, instruct, oral, theory, illustrate, probe, diagnose, consequence, version, create, dilute, skeletal, novel, threshold, technology, element, dynamic, challenge, typical, transfer, aspect, diet, cohort, external, vector, antibiotic, domain, temporary, linear, plus, digit, accurate, concept, transport, rotate, input, absorb, replicate, distinct, radical, superior, contact, ensure, stable, prevalence, capture, degrade, anesthesia, optimal, kit, bias, proximal, constant, incorporate, sufficient, sustain, label, barrier, zone, chart, implement, trauma, fnd, context, hence, community, lateral, facilitate, trim, prolong, quantify, perception, accumulate, expert, grant, amplification, random, construct, mount, renal, enviroment, couple, laser, magnitude, formula, deficit, alter, access, supplement, eliminate, graph, shift, capacity, qualitative, simulate, globe, modulate, output, attenuate, statistic, prescribe, differentiate, equivalent, orient, practitioner, substantial, chemical, thereby, onset, intake, stane, trend, overnight, contribute, enable, spectrum, assign, option, implicate, aid, tag, portion, electron, cope, decline, species, unique, overlap, adjacent, node, transform, modify, manual, colleague, core, entry, deficient, cascade, benefit, identical, parallel, migrate, reagent, exceed, comprise, highlight, evolution, schedule, organism, predominant, cumulative, purchase, plot, seek, emerge, affinity valid, code, sterile, compute, prospect, utilize, eposit, column, contract, scar, axis, inferior, deviate, trigger, loop, precursor, perceive, preliminary, undertake, substitute, whilst, scenario, adapt, adult, expand, cord, fundamental, feedback, sum, elicit, circulation, tolerance, team, se, candidate, assume, imply, terminal, vascular, hormone, minor, panel, aggressive, comprehensive, residual, perspective, brief, trace, quip, accelerate, template, mode, diminish, consecutive, foundational, emphasize, physiology, oxide, restore, conflict, phenomenon, invade, restrict, attach, longitude, technical, nevertheless, append, infiltrate, bacteria, agonist, rely, capable, manipulate, histology, pharmacology, saline, persist, integrity, precede, rear, mental, demographic, pathology, prominent,

apparatus, paradigm, adjust, crucial, nervous, gradient, disrupt, encounter, nitrogen, format, robust, spontaneous, principal, transmit, audit, decade, comprise, cue, gland, assist, inner, intrinsic, consume, suppress, fragment, hypertension, placebo, dominant, text, susceptible, spinal, corporate, principle, relapse, numerical, resolve, mature, uniform, diverse, retain, abdominal, lane, vital, suspend, voluntary, diffuse, rationale, simultaneous, transient, secrete, methanol, confer, constitute, accomplish, enroll, embryo, logistic, project, insight, compliance, emission, soluble, comment, oxygen, warrant, route, morbidity, widespread, alcohol, conjugate, acknowledge, alternative, manifest, cluster, notion, render, malignancy, resemble, obvious, antigen, concomitant, fusion, elucidate, consensus, file, biology, urban verify, speculate, postulate, routine, somewhat, catheter, odd, discrete, converse, span, augment, depict, adequate, neutral, thereafter, annual, plastic, professional, recall, entity, precise, successive, contaminate, tone, integrate, confound, profound, tension, dramatic, blast, encompass, consult, static.

The full Medical Academic Vocabulary List (MAVL) is available at [EAP Foundation](#)

Final 50 MAVL Words for Quiz:

acid; approximate; available; bacteria; buffer; calcium; capable; capacity; cell; chemical; code; conjugate; constant; contract; converse; create; define; dimension; distinct; display; diverse; donor; enzyme; formation; function; hormone; amino; infect; linear; link; obtain; occur; peptide; plasma; predominant; primary; process; protein; react; recall; regulate; release; secondary; species; specific; structure; unique; virus; neutral; target;